

TRANSPORT NUMBERS OF AQUEOUS SILVER NITRATE IN PRÉSENCE OF SUCROSE AND MEASUREMENTS OF CONDUCTIVITY, VISCOSITY, DENSITY AND REFRACTIVITY

BY DUSHYANT NARASINGASA SOLANRI AND SHANKARANAND MUKERJI

Transport number measurements have been made at 25° for aqueous silver nitrate ($M/18$) in presence of varying proportions of sucrose. The minimum in the transport number-sucrose concentration curve has been attributed to the changes in the degree of hydration of sucrose. Data are also given for the conductivity, viscosity, density and refractivity of the corresponding solutions.

The most extensive series of experiments on migration ratios is that of Hittorf (*Ann. Physik*, 1853, 80, 177; 1859, 106, 337, 513), the earliest worker in the field. Noyes (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1901, 36, 63; *Technology Quarterly*, 1904, 17, 4) made exact measurements of the migration ratios for a large number of salts. Steele (*Phil. Trans.*, 1902, 198A, 105) concluded that the only possible cause of variability in the migration ratio with concentration was the formation of complex ions.* Diverging views prevail in the literature (*cf.* Carrara, *Gazzetta*, 1903, 33, 241; Krumreich, *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1916, 22, 446) regarding the influence of the medium on the transport number of silver nitrate despite considerable work done in this field.** It was of interest, therefore, to investigate the influence of sucrose on the transport number, especially from the standpoint of corresponding changes in conductivity, viscosity, density and refractivity of the medium.

EXPERIMENTAL

The chemicals employed were Merck's guaranteed reagents. A stock solution of $M/9$ -AgNO₃ was prepared. In all the following experiments this stock solution was used either after proper dilution or with the appropriate addition of sucrose. The transport number apparatus used was the one devised by Findlay (*Chem. News*, 1909, 100, 185). It was first filled with $M/18$ -AgNO₃ solution to the mark taking sufficient precaution to avoid the introduction of air bubbles. It was then rigidly fixed and kept in an air-thermostat maintained at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. It was afterwards connected with a source of a.c. and a current of 12-13 milliamps. sent through the solution for 2½ hours. The electrodes used were of pure silver. The current was obtained by tapping off a suitable potential from a 220 volt D. C. main. A milliammeter and a copper voltameter were also inserted in the circuit, in series. The coulometer solution was prepared according to Ottel's recommendations (*Chem. Ztg.*, 1893, 17, 543). The copper plate to be used as cathode was first cleaned and weighed; and at the conclusion of the experiment it was withdrawn from the solution, washed well with distilled water and with alcohol, dried in the hot air over a flame, cooled and again weighed. While the experiment was in progress a slow stream of hydrogen, washed by bubbling through water, was passed through the coulometer solution in order to keep it stirred (*cf.* also Richards, Collins, and Heimrod, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1900, 32, 321).

* *cf.* also Noyes (*loc. cit.*): Bein (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1898, 27, 1; 1899, 28, 439); Cantelo and Payne (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1932, 36, 1045).

** *cf.* Schlundt (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1902, 6, 159); Carrara (*loc. cit.*); Jones and Bassett (*Amer. Chem. J.*, 1904, 32, 409); Jones and Rouiller (*ibid.*, 1906, 38, 427); Sachanov and Grinbaum (*J. Russ. Phys. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 47, 1769); Krumreich (*loc. cit.*).

At the conclusion of the experiment, the rubber tube connecting the anode and the middle compartments was closed by means of a clip, and the anode liquid run off, through the tap at the bottom of the anode tube, into a graduated cylinder. This tube and the electrode were then washed out with a little of the original solution, which was also collected in the cylinder and the volume noted. The composition of this, and of the original solution was determined volumetrically. Since the concentration changes on electrolysis in the vicinity of the electrodes are usually less, a slight error in the analysis will affect the transport number value to a considerable extent. Repeated analyses had therefore to be carried out to get the required accuracy. The solution from the middle compartment after electrolysis was also analysed from time to time and was found to remain almost unaltered in composition. From the increase, on electrolysis, of Ag-ion concentration in the anode compartment, the transport number of the cation was computed. The above quantity has been measured for $M/18\text{-AgNO}_3$ in presence of varying proportions of sucrose as shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Influence of sucrose

Conc. of AgNO_3 in the mixture = $M/18$. Temp. = $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. Current = 12.13 milliamps.
Duration of electrolysis = $2\frac{1}{2}$ hrs.

Amounts of sucrose in 100 c.c. soln.	Transport No. of Ag.*	Specific conductivity.	Viscosity (μ .) centipoises.	Relative density.	Refractive index. (n_D).	
0 g.	0.473 0.473 0.474	0.473	0.00655 mhos.	1.020	1.008	1.33329
2.5	0.454 0.455 0.459	0.456	0.00614	0.981	1.017	1.33676
5.0	0.441 0.443 0.439	0.441	0.00584	1.025	1.027	1.34046
10.0	0.434 0.430 0.435	0.433	0.00516	1.173	1.046	1.34718
15.0	0.468 0.469 0.464	0.467	0.00462	1.363	1.065	1.35456

To obtain further information in regard to the above results the corresponding electrolytic conductivity was determined on a Pye's modified Post Office box with the usual precautions (*cf.* Joshi and Solanki, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 14, 323; 1940, 17, 627). The cell constant, determined by using $N/50\text{-KCl}$, was found to be 0.3777. These results are given in column 3, Table I.

The viscosity and relative density determinations were also made at 25° for each of the above mixtures and are shown in Table I. The refractive indices for the sodium line corresponding to these were determined by means of Pulfrich refractometer at the above temperature and these results are given in Table I.

All these results are shown graphically in Fig. 1. The quantities, *viz.*, transport number, specific conductivity, viscosity, relative density, and refractive index, are plotted against concentration of sucrose in the mixture by approximate selection of scale units in the same figure (*cf.* curves 1-5 in Fig. 1).

DISCUSSION

The transport number of an ion depends, besides the factors like temperature, valency, concentration and the nature of the solute and the other ion with which it is associated, upon the specific behaviour, the dielectric constant and the viscosity of the medium. The abnormalities in the above quantity especially in stronger solutions are usually attributed to the formation of molecular or ionic complexes in the conducting medium, owing to the interaction of the ions with the solute or the solvent molecules.

Results in column 2, Table I indicate that the transport number of Ag^+ -ion diminishes progressively with the increase in concentration of sucrose till it attains the minimum value in the vicinity of 10%, and then suddenly rises (*cf.* curve 1, Fig. 1). To account for the observed results, the following disturbing factors need be considered: (i) hydration of the cation, $[\text{Ag}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_n]^+$; (ii) complex formation of Ag^+ -ion with sucrose molecules, $[\text{Ag}(\text{sucrose})_n]^+$, (iii) hydration of sucrose $[\text{sucrose } n(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$.

(i) and (ii) might bring about the migration of water and sucrose molecules respectively along with Ag^+ -ion, with a concomitant change in the concentration of sucrose. Polarimetric observations of the solutions *after* migration, however, indicated no measurable changes in the sucrose concentration in the anode and cathode compartments. Washburn (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 81, 322), however, observed a change in concentration of the reference substance (sucrose or raffinose) after electrolysis; this was maximum in the case of LiCl and minimum in KCl . It appears, therefore, that (i) and (ii) are not operative. Furthermore, Ag^+ -ion being relatively a heavier ion might show very little tendency for hydration, since ions of lighter elements are more highly hydrated. The observed changes in the transport number value might be due principally to an increase in hydration of sucrose with its increased concentration, followed by a diminution in solvation. Among other physical factors influencing the mobility of an ion, reference should particularly be made to the dielectric constant of the medium and

the specific frictional coefficient of the ions especially at higher concentrations of sucrose. Furthermore, sucrose at a high concentration might disturb the homogeneity of the AgNO_3 solution by forming the colloidal silver particles by reduction, as evident from the blackening of the solution.

When transference numbers in different solvents are considered there are found many inexplicable anomalies. Attempt at arriving at any generalisation has been found impossible owing to the fact that the above measurements by different authors have produced divergent data. To quote a few: Schlundt (*loc. cit.*) determined the transport number of Ag^+ -ion from AgNO_3 in water and in various organic liquids; Jones and Basset (*loc. cit.*) and Jones and Rouiller (*loc. cit.*) measured the transport number in water, methyl and ethyl alcohols, acetone and in binary mixtures of these solvents together with the conductivity of such solutions; Sachanov and Grinbaum (*loc. cit.*) conducted measurements in aniline, pyridine and in mixed solutions of the two; Carrara (*loc. cit.*) in methyl alcohol; and Krumreich (*loc. cit.*) in ethyl alcohol-water mixtures. Their results and interpretations differ very widely.

Kruger (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1916, 22, 445) on theoretical grounds, concluded that the transport numbers of a given pair of ions should tend to the same value in all non-associated solvents. In associated solvents, and when solvation occurs, the values differ. He remarks that in dilute solutions, the above values for AgNO_3 are practically independent of the nature of the solvent (*cf.* also Sachanov, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1917, 21, 166). Kruger believes that the effect of the solvent may be covered, in a simple case, by its viscosity: $u\eta = c_1$ and $v\eta = c_2$, where u and v are the mobilities and c_1 , c_2 are constants.

It became necessary for the interpretation of the results obtained to determine the specific conductivity, viscosity, density and refractivity of the solutions used in this work. These data are shown in Table I and graphically in curves 2-5 in Fig. 1. The linear relationship of specific conductivity, density and of refractivity with concentration of sucrose, as revealed by the respective straight line graphs (*cf.* curves 2, 4 and 5 in Fig. 1) suggests that these measurements seem to throw practically no light in accounting for the minimum in the transport number curve. The viscosity graph exhibits a minimum in the neighbourhood of 3% (*cf.* curve 3 in Fig. 1), which it is difficult to account for. It is interesting, however, to note that the variations of viscosity and transport number are of the same nature, though the actual positions of the minima are not the same. It is seen that the effect of changing viscosity on the addition of sucrose is important in affecting the conductance and the ionic mobilities, but no general conclusions can, apparently, be drawn (*cf.* also Partington, Taylor's "Treatise on Physical Chemistry," MacMillan and Co. Ltd., London, 1931, Vol. I, p. 729).

Our best thanks are due to Dr. S. S. Joshi, Head of the Department of Chemistry, for valuable help and suggestions during the course of this work.